

CURRENT TRENDS IN SPATIAL ANALYSIS OF ZOOBOTIC DISEASES IN INDIA

**G. Satya Mohana Venkatesh^{1*}, Bhanu Rekha V², Sangeetha. D¹,
Nithya Quintoil M³, Ajay Kumar V.J⁴**

¹MVSc Scholar, Department of Veterinary Public Health and Epidemiology, RIVER, Puducherry, ²Professor and Head, Department of Veterinary Public Health and Epidemiology, RIVER, Puducherry, ³Assistant Professor, Department of Veterinary Public Health and Epidemiology, RIVER, Puducherry, ⁴Professor, Department of Veterinary Public Health and Epidemiology, RIVER, Puducherry.

Corresponding author email: gsmvenkatesh1178@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

In India, the zoonotic diseases surge has become a great concern to the Human and animal health. The zoonotic diseases like rabies, brucellosis, toxoplasmosis, cysticercosis, echinococcosis, Japanese encephalitis (JE), leptospirosis, scrub typhus, nipah, trypanosomiasis, Kyasanur forest disease (KFD), and Crimean-Congo haemorrhagic fever mainly affects public health in India. These diseases showing greater economic impact and leads to economic losses for farmers. Hence, epidemiological measures like spatial analysis is essential for prior identification of these outbreaks. The spatial analysis of zoonotic diseases has gained significant momentum in India, driven by the increased frequency of zoonotic outbreaks and advancements in geospatial technologies, which takes into account the location and timing of events in order to find patterns, trends, and linkages within data. Recent trends emphasise the inclusion of spatial modelling and spatiotemporal analysis, geospatial clustering analysis, temporal analysis, spatial autocorrelation and spectral analysis to map disease distribution, identify hotspots and predict future outbreaks. Spatial statistics is used to analyse complex interactions between environment, animals, and humans. The One Health approach serves as a suitable framework for conducting spatial analysis. Analysing and understanding the latest trends in spatial analysis play an important role in predicting outbreaks and protecting public health in the future.

KEYWORDS: Spatial analysis, Zoonotic disease, Spatiotemporal analysis, Outbreaks, Risk map.

INTRODUCTION

Spatial analysis is a group of techniques for drawing new insights from spatial data. It covers geographic data analysis, visualization, sampling, and manipulation. For a variety of datasets, spatial analysis can help with decision-making, scientific discovery, and the provision of useful information (Hao, Pu. 2019). Zoonotic diseases (ZD) are illnesses that originate in animals and are transmitted to humans either spontaneously or through zoonotic vectors

from zoonotic reservoirs (ZR). Emerging diseases scrub typhus, cutaneous leishmaniasis, and Japanese encephalitis are examples of newly evolved diseases that are now rapidly spreading to new geographical area, new host, or wide vector ranges due to their changing ecology (Dhiman, R. C., & Tiwari, A. 2018). For the purpose of tracking and forecasting diseases, spatial analysis is a crucial procedure for identifying essential and validated risk factors. Disease prediction can